

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	09	11	Macapa	N	00	02.070	E	-051	02.323
End	2021	09	18	Belém	N	01	26.910	E	-048	30.047

CAMPAING OBJECTIVE

This leg was mainly dedicated to study the effect of the Amazon River over the Atlantic Microbiome. Besides, as rivers act as an important road for plastics getting into the ocean, we also focused on the study of the microplastics and those microbes living the plastic fragments (constituting the plastisphere).

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Martin Hertau
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Yves Tournon
3	CREW - Mecano	Loic Caudan
4	CREW - Deck	David Monmarche
5	CREW - Deck	Francois Aurat
6	CREW - Cook	Sophie Bin
7	CREW - Media	Maeva Bardy
8	GUEST - Artist	-
9	GUEST - Observer	Guilherme Cajueiro
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Josep Maria Erta Montejo (JE) / Alison Chase (AC)
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	Helena Cruz de Carvalho (HCC)
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Douglas Couet (DC)
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Paula Huber (PH)
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Xiomara Francesca Garcia Diaz (XD)
15	SCIENCE - F - additional	

SAMPLING STRATEGY & ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

We performed two stations (041 - 042). The station 041 was done in the Bay of Macapá (Amazon River system) and the station 042 in shallow waters of the Amazon plume with surface freshwater.

Station 041 was done upstream of Macapá city as a reference for “less impacted water” comparing with the 040 (from leg 5). The sampling was performed during the High-to-Low (HT-LT; ebb) and Low-High (LT-HT; flood) tides cycles.

Station 042 was performed in North Brazilian Current, upstream of the Amazon plume, as reference of surface freshwater condition. The sampling was performed during the day and night, at surface and one epipelagic depth (DCM).

Figure 1. Sampling stations (041 & 042) location performed during the leg 6 (MM- Macapá-Belém). a) Chlorophyll; b) Sea Surface Salinity; c) Sea Surface Height. The maps were provided by Lea Olivier (locean-ipsl).

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

See Campaign Summary Report for Leg 7

CP50	petri-slide												
SCP50	petri-slide												
F200	250-mL-bottle												
E200	15-mL-falcon												
S200	5-mL-cryotube												
S200-L	5-mL-falcon												
PM-HG200	Zip-lock												
MB200	4-mL-Vial												
CP200	petri-slide												
F680	250-mL-bottle												
F2000	250-mL-bottle												
E680	15-mL-falcon												
S680-L	MULTIPLATES												
E2000	15-mL-falcon												
AI	petri-slide												
AS	2-mL-cryotube												
AF	Zip-lock												
SP300	2-mL-cryotube												
MP300	2-mL-cryotube												
CP300	petri-slide												
TOC	30-mL-bottle												
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube												
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube												
S025-L	15-mL-falcon												
S520-L	5-mL-falcon												
FM5	5-mL-falcon												
MTE-BP	125-mL Bottle												
	TOTAL	154	47	46	50	0	50	180	105	9	168	140	120